

“The last enemy that shall be destroyed is death” On Adam, Hades, and Nubian Triumphal Crosses

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INTRODUCTION¹

Large ornamental crosses belong to the most impressive compositions in the painted decoration of Nubian churches². Whereas most cross types in Nubian ornamental programmes are familiar to the Christian world around the Mediterranean, some designs or elements of crosses are characteristic for the Middle Nile Valley, the territory of Nubia. This study explores an often-neglected element of a group of Nubian crosses: the bearded head, impaled under the foot of the cross.

The most prominent exclusively Nubian cross composition is the so-called *Maiestas Crucis*: a richly bejewelled or plain Latin or Greek cross with a bust of Christ in a medallion or square on the intersection of the cross beams, and surrounding Him, in the quarters of the cross, the Four Living Creatures³. This intricate design refers to the triumphal Second Coming of Christ at the end of times (the *Parousia*) when the sign of the Son of Man (the Cross) will appear in the sky (Mt. 24:30). He is accompanied by the Living Creatures, who sing his glory. The composition has received ample scholarly attention through the years, focussing on the iconography and the iconology of the cross, Christ, and the heavenly beings⁴.

The first cross of this type to be discovered was painted in the so-called Rivergate Church in Pachoras/Faras (hereafter Faras) in Nobadia, Lower Nubia, which was excavated in 1911-1912 by the British archaeologist Francis Llewellyn Griffith and his team. The Greek cross was painted on the west face of the north-eastern pillar and part of the soffit of the arch, above the steps of the pulpit of the church. A *velum* was draped over the top of the cross and over the horizontal arms; Christ was depicted in the centre and the Four Living Creatures in the quarters. Griffith wrote that the “... cross ends below in a spearhead, transfixing the bearded head of Adam.” To the right of the

spearhead, a donor (a priest or bishop), was depicted; to the left a votive inscription. The composition was painted on a white background; outlines were mainly in black and the only colours used were red and yellow ochre, and white (Catalogue – no. 5; Pl. 5)⁵. The inscription mentions

¹ Quotation in title from 1 Corinthians 15:26. This article was written in the framework of the project ‘Frontier Wanderings, Church Decoration in the Aswan Region and in Lower Nubia (sixth-fifteenth century)’, National Science Centre Poland, Polonez 3 2016/23/P/HS3/04153. The project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement no. 665778. This article could not have been written without the continuous help and support of Dobrochna Zielińska and Adam Łajtar, my friends, colleagues, and partners in this project. They have welcomed me as a newcomer in the field of Nubian studies, educated me, encouraged my ‘views from outside’ and saved me from errors and pitfalls (needless to say that all remaining errors are my own).

² See for an introduction to Christian Nubia, for example, van Gerven Oei/Tsakos 2020, 204-206. For an overview of church buildings and wall paintings, see Godlewski 1992; *idem* 1996.

³ The Book of Revelation (4:6-8) describes the Living Creatures as four heavenly beings with the heads of a lion, man, eagle, and an ox who surround the throne of God and who praise Him continuously.

⁴ Van Moorsel 1966; *idem* 1972; Dobrzeński 1974; Dinkler 1975, 25-26; van Moorsel in van Moorsel/Jacquet/Schneider 1975; Kühnel 1992. Kühnel divides the *Maiestas Crucis* into two types: A) a cross with Christ and the Four Living Creatures; and B) Christ and the Four Living Creatures with a cross. In the latter case, the figures are painted larger in size with the cross disappearing into the background. These types are designated by Innemée/Zielińska (2018, 620) as ‘standing’ and ‘floating’ crosses.

⁵ Griffith 1926, 79-80, 92 and Pls XLVI (plan), LVI-1, LVII and LXV-14. The upper part of the painting fell down a few days after discovery (Griffith 1926, 79). The site was flooded by Lake Nasser/Nubia in the 1960s. Griffith describes the Four Living Creatures each as “... the emblem of an Evangelist.” In Western iconography, familiar to European archaeologists, the Four Living Creatures symbolise the Evangelists and the assumption that this was also

Goassi or Joassi, a priest. It is not certain whether he was the donor or a later visitor⁶. The painting belonged to the second phase of decoration of the church, which is dated to the second half of the twelfth-fifteenth centuries⁷.

Griffith consulted with the Reverend C.R.D. Biggs on the interpretation of the wall paintings⁸. For the cross, Biggs explained that the skull of Adam had been found at Golgotha ('the place of a skull'), the location where Christ was crucified. When His blood dripped through a fissure in the rock upon Adam's skull, Christ, as the second Adam, redeemed the sins of the first Adam: "It is to this belief that we trace the representation of a skull at the foot of the Crucifix." The explanation builds on 1 Corinthians 15, especially verse 22: "For as in Adam all die, even so in Christ all shall be made alive"⁹.

the case in Christian Egypt and Nubia, lived on for a long time (see also Michałowski 1967, 161-162; Baldassarre 1967, 4). However, in Christian Egypt and Nubia, the Living Creatures, angelic beings who are in the immediate presence of God and unceasingly worship Him, are seen as intermediaries between God and mankind (Müller 1959, 83-84; de Grooth/van Moorsel 1977/1978; Kühnel 1992, 191).

⁶ Griffith 1926, 79 and Pls LVII, LXV-14. Translation and remark: Adam Łajtar.

⁷ Martens-Czarnecka 1992, 376; van Moorsel dates the painting to the beginning of the eleventh century (van Moorsel/Jacquet/Schneider 1975, 113).

⁸ Griffith 1926, 56.

⁹ Griffith 1926, 80.

¹⁰ Jakobielski and Martens-Czarnecka express some doubt in their description of one of the Faras crosses (Catalogue – no. 3), stating the head is "... traditionally identified as the head of Adam." (Jakobielski *et al.* 2017, 268).

¹¹ Tenth-twelfth century examples in Schiller 1967, Figs 336-337, 340-344.

¹² Van Moorsel 1966; *idem* 1972; Dobrzeński 1974; Kühnel 1992. A shaft/spike under the cross in the Central Church of Abdallah-n Irqi (Catalogue – no. 13; Pl. 15) is visible in one of the excavation photographs (Leiden, Rijksmuseum van Oudheden (RMO), Archive Shokan-Abdallah-n Irqi 8.2.2b_17a, photo 27). This element disappeared during the painting transfer. It was not copied in the line drawing of the cross, nor is it mentioned in the description (van Moorsel/Jacquet/Schneider 1975, 72, Fig. 6/4 on p. 72, 111-112). With many thanks to Mariëlle Bulsink and Lara Weiss (RMO) for their help.

¹³ Frazer investigated a Byzantine tenth-century ivory with the crucifixion of Christ, in which a reclining figure is stabbed in the stomach by the cross (Frazer 1974, 155: "Since Christ's crucifixion redeemed Adam, why should he be portrayed as disembowelled by the instrument of his salvation?").

The tradition that Golgotha was the place where Adam was buried and where the wood of the Cross redeemed the sin caused by the wood/tree of forbidden fruits in Paradise, was in Byzantine art often indicated by the 'skull of Adam', which is depicted below the cross in representations of the Crucifixion from the ninth century onwards (see below). This concept was a plausible explanation for a head under a cross for early archaeologists and scholars working in Nubia and it gained credibility when in the 1960s, the inscription 'Adam' was found to the right of the hemisphere holding the spearhead piercing a head under a cross in the cathedral of Faras (Catalogue – no. 3; Pl. 3)¹⁰. Likewise, the latter cross belongs to the *Maiestas Crucis* type. In the meantime, a spike, spearhead, or spear point blade transfixing a head or with its point resting on a head was also found in other cross compositions. In Sonqi Tino and Tamit (Church of Angels), for example, it can be found under an ornate cross draped with a large cloth, a *velum* (end ninth-beginning eleventh centuries and thirteenth-fourteenth centuries; see Catalogue – nos 1, Pl. 1, and 6, Pl. 6).

There are, however, fundamental differences between the skull in Byzantine images on the one hand, and the head in the Nubian compositions on the other hand. In the first case, the 'skull of Adam' is depicted as a skull. It is found in Crucifixion scenes, picturing the death of Christ, the culmination of His suffering: the skull, standing, in vertical position, rests at the foot of the cross or is placed in a kind of fissure or small cave in the hill upon which the cross stands¹¹. In Nubia though, a head with features, hair, moustache and beard, lying on one side, in a horizontal position, is impaled or is at the point of being impaled by a spike under the shaft of a triumphal, glorious cross, referring to resurrection and salvation, Christ's Second Coming and the Heavenly Jerusalem.

The 'head of Adam' is often mentioned in passing in iconographical and iconological studies on Nubian crosses. It was never studied properly, and the spike or spearhead seems to have been ignored completely¹². Nonetheless, despite the inscription 'Adam' in the painting in Faras Cathedral, was this head truly meant to represent Adam? Or, to paraphrase Margaret English Frazer: Since Christ's crucifixion redeemed Adam, why should he be portrayed as impaled by the instrument of his salvation¹³?

Up till now, six crosses ending in a spike and transfixing a head have been documented in churches in the Middle Nile Valley, both in Nobadia and Makuria (see Catalogue – nos 1-6; Pls 1-6): in Sonqi Tino (end ninth-beginning eleventh centuries), Faras (three crosses in the cathedral, late tenth century, early eleventh century, and eleventh-thirteenth centuries; Rivergate Church, twelfth-fifteenth centuries?) and in the Church of Angels at Tamit (thirteenth-fourteenth centuries). Four crosses show (part of) a spike (Church of Raphael in Tamit, tenth-eleventh centuries), North-West Annex of the Monastery on Kom H in Old Dongola (first half twelfth century), and Faras Cathedral, early eleventh century and late thirteenth century or later; see Catalogue – nos 7-10; Pls 7-12) and nos 9-10 may have preserved traces of a head (Pls 11-12). A head is depicted under the base of a large cross in the church in the temple of Wadi es-Sebua, in a similar position as the transfixed heads but, as far as we can see, there is no spike (Catalogue – no. 11; Pl. 13).

In two examples in Faras Cathedral (first half of tenth century and early eleventh century), it is highly probable that a spike and head were part of the composition. A cross in the Church of Abdallah-n Irqi (tenth century) stands on a partly preserved shaft (see note 12 and Catalogue – nos 12-14; Pls 14-16). Partly preserved monumental crosses without traces of a spike and/or head are not included in the catalogue and will not be included in this study.

Apart from one of the crosses in Faras Cathedral, which is not an official painting but more a drawing of a private nature or maybe a sketch (Catalogue – no. 4; Pl. 4)¹⁴, common ground is their large size. Even if the measurements of some crosses are not known, the archaeological context makes clear that they must have been quite large.

The basic type is a Greek or Latin cross with straight or slightly flared arms. Nearly all crosses are highly ornamental and are decorated with painted gemstones in various colours and pearl borders. The small cross in Faras Cathedral, the Rivergate Church cross, and the cross in the Church of Angels in Tamit are an exception (Catalogue – nos 4-6; Pls 4-6). The arms of the small Faras cross are plain with a square at the ends filled with a nimbbed head, followed by an ogee pointed ornament¹⁵. The

plain arms of the Rivergate Church and the Church of Angels crosses end in trefoils. All three are draped with a *velum*, as is the cross in Sonqi Tino (Catalogue – no. 1; Pl. 1), whose straight arms, set with gems, have small transverse beams as terminals.

The small cross in Faras Cathedral and the Rivergate Church cross combine the *velum* with the *Maiestas Crucis*: Christ in a square or medallion on the intersection of the cross beams and the Four Living Creatures in the quarters¹⁶. Apart from two fragmentary paintings, whose design cannot be fully reconstructed (Catalogue – nos 8, Pl. 10, and 12, Pl. 14), the Faras crosses (Catalogue – nos 2-5, 10, 14) are all of the *Maiestas Crucis* type in which no. 10 takes a unique place: Christ is replaced by the Trinity and the enthroned Virgin and Child are added. Almost all the crosses have chains with bells linking the cross arms. In Faras Cathedral, the base of crosses nos 3 (Pl. 3) and 14 (Pl. 16) are flanked by twigs with red fruit or flowers while the horizontal arms and the top of crosses nos 2 (Pl. 2) and 12 (Pl. 14) sprout short branches. Most of the crosses rest on a hemisphere or a node/sphere, which in some cases rest on a stepped base. Under this hemispherical or triangular foot, or directly under the cross shaft, a spike points down and stabs a head.

The Wadi es-Sebua cross (Catalogue – no. 11; Pl. 13) is slightly different. It is a large bejewelled cross and from the intersection of the cross beams radiate branches with a flower or piece of fruit at the end. The cross rests on an irregular base with a doorway with a keyhole shaped entrance. The

¹⁴ Ratyński 1982, 270. With my sincere thanks to Stefan Jakobielski for providing detailed information on this drawing.

¹⁵ The only other Nubian example of such a design was painted in the so-called Throne Hall of the Makurian court at Old Dongola (western part of north wall, ninth century). Christ is depicted in the centre of an equal armed cross. Instead of their usual place in the quarters, the Four Living Creatures are depicted in medallions on the cross arms (Zielińska 2015, 35, Figs 2-16, 17; Innemée/Zielińska 2018, 615-616, Figs 1-2).

¹⁶ The cross in the Church of Angels in Tamit (Catalogue – no. 6; Pl. 6) shows part of the outline of a medallion on the intersection of the cross beams. The interior of the medallion is damaged but there are certainly no Living Creatures depicted in the quarters. Nor Monneret de Villard (1935/1957, vol. I, 158), nor Baldassarre (1967, 57-58) mention the medallion.

head under the cross is not as detailed or competently painted as the cross itself and might have been a later addition.

The documented examples were painted in the nave or aisles of a church and most of these paintings were donated¹⁷. An image of a male donor was found near the crosses in the Rivergate Church in Faras and the Central Church at Abdallah-n Irqi, while a female donor was depicted in the Church of Raphael in Tamit (Catalogue – nos 5, 13, and 7: Pls 5, 15, and 7-9). Donors were probably also depicted near a cross in the church in the temple at Wadi es-Sebua and in Faras Cathedral (Catalogue – nos 11-12; Pls 13-14). In Faras Cathedral, the two crosses in the northern vestibule (Catalogue – nos 3, Pl. 3, and 14, Pl. 16) were donated by women as shown by inscriptions. The ladies did not leave their portraits. Other inscriptions are (secondary) prayers and legends: *stauros*, ‘cross’, the names of Christ and the Living Creatures and in one case ‘Adam’ to the right of the hemisphere holding the spearhead (Faras Cathedral, Catalogue – no. 3; Pl. 3) or biblical/liturgical phrases (the

three times *agios* sung by the Living Creatures, as reported in the Book of Revelation 4:8)¹⁸.

TRIUMPHAL CROSSES

From an instrument of a humiliating, terrible death, the cross quickly became a sign of triumph, a sign of victory. Through his death on the cross, Christ redeemed mankind and gave it new life. The Cross became a symbol of protection, deliverance, and a promise of a better life to come. Church fathers like Cyril of Jerusalem (d. 386) wrote: “... a sign of a luminous Cross precedes the King, showing Him who was formerly crucified...” referring to the ‘the Sign of the Son of Man’ appearing in the sky before Christ’s second coming (Mt. 24:30)¹⁹. As such, it encompasses the past (the historical event: the Crucifixion) and the eschatological future. At the same time, representations of the Cross function in the present. Visual art expresses these registers, merging and overlapping, in form, decoration and attributes as well as in the purpose and use of cross-shaped objects or objects decorated with crosses or – in the case of wall paintings – in the location where crosses were depicted²⁰.

Numerous homilies and hymns (Greek, Coptic, Old Nubian) sing the glory, protective and life-giving qualities of the Holy Cross as well as its destructive power against all things iniquitous and bad²¹. As Robin Jensen writes, the Cross “... was more than a mere sign: it was a potent indicator of God’s power and intention to destroy evil, sin, and death”²².

The Triumphal Cross, the symbol of the resurrected Christ and his Second Coming on the Day of Judgement, was depicted as a gem-studded cross of gold or silver or, in case of objects, was a gold or silver cross, set with coloured gemstones, crystals and pearls. Pearls and gems or alpha and omega symbols might hang from the horizontal cross arms. The glittering gold, crystal, pearls, and gems echo the image of the Heavenly Jerusalem as described in the Book of Revelation (21:10-23): A city of gold, clear as crystal, the foundations of the walls adorned with precious stones, with gates of pearls.

Gemmed crosses as objects were made as reliquaries for relics of the True Cross, that, according to tradition, was found by the Empress Helena, mother of the Emperor Constantine the Great²³. They were mounted on staffs as processional crosses

¹⁷ As has already been noted by van Moorsel (1966, 309-310) for the *Maiestas Crucis* type, which was the focus of his study. See also Kühnel 1992, 191; Martens-Czarnecka 1992, 375.

¹⁸ The chant of the Living Creatures (the Trisagion) has found its way into liturgical prayers and magical spells (Müller 1959, 83-84, with references to liturgical and magical texts; van Moorsel 1966, 301-303; van Moorsel in van Moorsel/Jacquet/Schneider 1975, 112; Kühnel 1992, 191).

¹⁹ Cyril of Jerusalem, *Catechetical Lecture (Lenten Lecture)* 15:22 (translation McCauly in McCauly/Stephenson 1970, 68).

²⁰ I have initially explored this theme, the timespan of past-present-future in symbolic meaning, function, and ritual in the decoration of churches in Christian Egypt (van Loon 1999, see also van Loon in Gabra/van Loon 2012, 30-31). For Nubia, Adam Łajtar and Dobrochna Zielińska (2016) have investigated the northern pastophorium of churches and its decoration in a similar theoretical framework.

²¹ On Nubian Cross- or *Stauros*-hymns, see Browne 1983; Tsakos *et al.* 2013. For *Stauros*-hymns in the homilies attributed to Ps. Theophilus of Alexandria (*Sermo de cruce et latrone*) and Ps. Chrysostom (*In venerabilem crucem sermo*) in various languages, see Suciú 2012; van Gerven Oei/Tsakos 2020, 210-218.

²² See for the various themes Jensen 2017. Quote in Jensen 2017, 27.

²³ For the traditions of the Finding of the True Cross (*Inventio Crucis*), see Jensen 2017, 56-62. On cross reliquaries, see Jensen 2017, 109-111. See also note 42.

and, as early as the fourth century, placed in churches and played a role in the liturgy²⁴. Processions with crosses could welcome or accompany dignitaries²⁵ and crosses acted in Byzantine imperial ceremonies²⁶, while monumental free-standing crosses, in public spaces or in churches are also recorded²⁷. Early representations of gemmed crosses can be found in the half domes of apses of churches and mausolea²⁸. These depictions of gemmed crosses imitate actual crosses: the pendants hanging on the arms, the pins set on the arms for candles, and the tangs to mount them on staffs or stick them in a foot or a base, and, in case of the Nubian crosses, the bell chains arranged between the cross arms²⁹.

In Egypt, Nubia's northern neighbour whose patriarchate was in charge of the Nubian Church, an abundance of richly decorated painted crosses appeared in monastic buildings of, for example, Kellia (sixth-eighth centuries)³⁰. Triumphal Crosses appeared in the naos, *khurus*, and the semi domes of the altar rooms or (apsidal) niches of churches³¹, in tombs³² and on textiles³³. In Nubia, as far as the archaeological record has shown, gemmed crosses are limited to wall paintings in churches and monastic buildings.

The *velum*, a long cloth draped over the horizontal cross beam has known a certain appreciation in Nubia and Egypt although it seems that it was not very popular in the early Christian and Byzantine world³⁴. Apart from the painted draped crosses mentioned above (Catalogue – nos 1, 4-6), the theme can be found in wall paintings of the churches of Abdallah-n Irqi and Abd'el Gadir³⁵. Among the examples in Egypt, the church on the hill of the monastery of Abu Fana near Mallawi (Middle Egypt) and the church of the Red Monastery near

or only the bishop (Barhebraeus, d. 1286, *Chronicon Ecclesiasticum*). Vantini 1975, 318, 421; see also Vantini 1970).

During the patriarchate of Michael I (744-768), on 17 Toth (14 September), the Feast of the Glorious Cross, a Nile inundation miracle took place. The patriarch, bishops, and clergy, carrying crosses and Gospel books, walked in a special procession to the Nile and prayed for the rise of the water (HPC III, 195 [449]; see also Hermann 1959, 46-47).

²⁶ Cotsonis 1994, 8-14; Flusin 2019. Innemée/Zielińska (2018) focus on this imperial connotation in relation to the painting of an elaborate cross in the so-called Throne Hall of the Makurian court at Old Dongola, mentioned above (note 15).

²⁷ Catalogue Princeton 2010, 12, 23 (S. Ćurčić); Innemée/Zielińska 2018, 618-619. For the discussion of the presence or absence of a monumental, gemmed cross on Golgotha before the end of the seventh century, see Milner 1996 and most recently *EEECA* 1, 566-567 (C. Milner).

²⁸ Churches: for example, the mosaics in Santa Pudenziana in Rome, early fifth century, San Apollinare in Classe, ca. 540, and the Chapel of Primus and Felicianus in San Stefano Rotondo in Rome, seventh century. Mausolea: for example, Galla Placidia, fifth century and Theodoric, sixth century, both in Ravenna. See Dinkler/Dinkler-von Schubert 1991, 98-107; Jensen 2017, 102-108; Innemée/Zielińska 2018, 618.

²⁹ This has long been recognized. Recently, see also Jensen 2017, 98; Innemée/Zielińska 2018, 621; Kitzinger 2019.

³⁰ *EEECA* 2, 12-14 (G. Descoedres); Spalding-Tracey 2020, 13-16.

³¹ For example, in Dayr as-Suryan, seventh-thirteenth centuries (Innemée 2016); Dayr al-Dik, fifth-sixth centuries (Martin 1971, 28-30; van Loon 2008, 183-190); Dayr al-Ganadla, sixth century (Buschhausen/Khorshid 1998); Dayr Abu Fana, church on the hill, ca. 1200 (Buschhausen 2003, 14 and Figs 5-8, 11; Martin 1972, 120-124 and Pl. XXII; Gabra/van Loon 2012, 242-245); White Monastery, thirteenth century? (Laferrière 2008: 1-17 and Pl. II; Gabra/van Loon 2012, 284-286; Bolman 2016, 213 and fig. 16.17).

³² For example, the so-called Tomb of Shenoute near the White Monastery, fifth century (Bolman/Davis/Pyke 2010; <https://www.360cities.net/image/tomb-of-st-shenoute-white-monastery-sohag-egypt>; Matjaž Kačičnik, accessed 20 December 2022)

³³ For example: Minneapolis Institute of Arts, inv. no. 83.126, fifth-sixth centuries (<https://collections.artsmia.org/art/3149/curtain-coptic>, accessed 4 February 2022); Jensen 2017, 99; two related wall hangings in Bern (Abegg Stiftung, inv. nos 2439 and 2638, fourth-sixth centuries) and in Stuttgart (Württembergisches Landesmuseum, inv. no. 1984-103; Schrenk 2004, 47-50).

³⁴ A rare example is the purple cloth draped on the horizontal arms of a gemmed cross standing on a throne in the Arian Baptistery in Ravenna (sixth century, https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Arian_Baptistry_ceiling_mosaic_-_Ravenna.jpg, accessed 20 December 2022).

³⁵ Abdallah-n Irqi: van Moorsel in van Moorsel/Jacquet/Schneider 1975, 69, 107, Fig. 60. Abd'el Gadir: Griffith 1928, 72 (no. 28), Pl. XXXIV-1; von Bissing 1937, 133-134, Pls 24b-25a.

²⁴ Jensen 2017, 91; *EEECA* 1, 377-378 (K. Sandin); Spalding-Tracey 2020, 105. For Byzantine processions in which crosses were carried and the use in liturgy, see Cotsonis 1994, 14-26. For Rome, see de Blaauw 2001.

²⁵ In a Sahidic text on John of Lycopolis, the saint tells the local clergy and the *archontes* of Assiut to receive a delegation of the emperor with the singing of psalms and hymns while holding Gospel books, and carrying crosses and censers (Devos 1970, 180-181; see also Spalding-Tracey 2020, 106). When the Nubian prince Georgios, son of king Zacharias, arrived in Baghdad in 836, he himself, courtiers and the bishop in his retinue carried golden crosses (Chronicle by Michael the Syrian, d. 1199 A.D.);

³⁶ Martin 1971, 46-47 and Figs 22-23; *idem* 1972, 120-121, Figs 1-3 and Pl. XXII; Buschhausen 2003, 14 and Figs 5-8, 11; Gabra/van Loon 2012, 242-245. The western wall with crosses, now part of a small courtyard, collapsed in December 2019 (<https://en.wataninet.com/main-hp/three-copts-dead-three-injured-as-wall-collapses-at-abu-fana-monastery/31194/>, accessed 20 December 2022).

³⁷ Laferrière 1993; Bolman 2016, 205-207, Fig. 16.1. Other draped crosses can be found in the Church of the Virgin in Dayr as-Suryan (tenth century), the Church of the Archangel Gabriel in Naqlun (Fayum), the White Monastery church (thirteenth century?) and in the Chapel of the Four Living Creatures in the Old Church of Dayr Anba Antunus (1232-1233 A.D.) (Spalding-Stracey 2020, 21; Godlewski 2000, 96; Laferrière 1993, Figs 18-19; *idem* 2008: 14-17 and Pl. II; Bolman 2002, Figs 4.40, 6.18-6.19; Gabra/van Loon 2012, 286 and 217; Bolman 2016, 213 and Fig. 16.17).

³⁸ The large crosses in the eastern semi-dome of the church of Dayr Abu Fana and the central cross on the west wall of the Red Monastery church have a curtain-like piece of fabric attached under the horizontal arms. In Dayr as-Suryan (*khurus*, south wall) a draped fabric attached to the top of the cross and the ends of the vertical beams, falls till the lower end of the horizontal beam.

³⁹ Colour based on descriptions and (if available) colour photographs. In Egypt, some of the White Monastery crosses have blue patterned cloths while in Dayr Anba Antunius and in Naqlun, the fabric is red patterned. In Dayr as-Suryan it is green.

⁴⁰ Baradez/Leglay 1957, 73-82; Storch 1971; Dinkler-von Schubert 1972; Laferrière 2008, 15-16 and Figs 9-11 (Deir al-Dik = Dayr Abu Fana). Curiously, the motif does not figure in encyclopaedia entries on crosses and cross-types. Elizabeth Bolman (2002, 75) noted the modern use of a draped cross during Lent, Easter, and Christmas in the Monastery of St Antony. Different colours were used for the various stages of the liturgical year. Such a cloth is seen as a burial shroud, part of the grave clothes found in the empty tomb as a sign of the risen Christ (John 20:1-9). See also Spalding-Stracey 2020, 108-109, 148-149.

⁴¹ See, for example, the Egyptian curtain mentioned above (note 33). Other examples: an engraving of a cross in a column of the Church of John the Evangelist in Ephesus, seventh century (Vikan 2010, Fig. 50) and the large cross in the semi dome of the apse of the Hagia Irene in Constantinople, eighth century (https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Church_of_St_Irene_0990.jpg, accessed 20 December 2022).

⁴² According to Dinkler/Dinkler-von Schubert (1991, 29), the *globusomphalos* refers to the Cross as the centre of the world. However, in this context, it is not the Cross but Golgotha, which was seen as such, see, for example, Sophronius of Jerusalem (d. 638), who explained in his *Anacreonticon* 20, 29: "... the Navel-point of the earth, that divine Rock in which was fixed the Wood which undid the curse of the tree." (Milner 1996, 94-95; Wilkinson 2002, 158). Contrary to the gospel accounts that Golgotha was on the outskirts of Jerusalem, as early as the mid-second century, church fathers developed the tradition that this hill was located in the centre of Jerusalem and subsequently, it was seen as the centre of the earth. Eusebius (*Vita Constantini* III.25) relates how the emperor Constan-

Sohag stand out. In Abu Fana, there are two large, draped crosses in two semi-domes of the eastern triconch and at least six draped crosses of various types on the former western wall of the church (probably ca. 1200)³⁶. In the Red Monastery church, five of the ten surviving painted crosses in the nave (before 1100?) have a *velum*³⁷.

The *velum* can be arranged in different ways. Most commonly, the textile is hanging in front or behind the cross shaft and is draped over the horizontal arms, the ends hanging down behind or in front³⁸. A Nubian variation, as in the drawing in Faras Cathedral, the Rivergate Church (Catalogue – nos 4-5; Pls 4-5), and the church at Abd'el Gadir, is arranging the cloth over the top of the cross. In the Rivergate Church, the *velum* hangs down on either side of the horizontal cross beam while in Abd'el Gadir and Faras the cloth goes around the cross and touches the base. The textile has in most cases a solid colour, a shade of red or purple, and sometimes a decorative border³⁹.

The cross draped with a *velum* is seen as having its origin in the *tropaion*, a military sign of victory after a battle where the mantle of the conquered adversary was arranged on a tree-like object, sometimes with branches as arms. Imperial connotations and Christ's Second Coming play a role, but its precise meaning still has to be investigated⁴⁰.

The hemisphere or node/sphere and/or the stepped triangular base of the crosses follow a more or less conventional pattern that can be traced to at least the fifth-sixth centuries⁴¹. The hemisphere or sphere, the *globus* or *omphalos*, literally 'the navel', may point to Golgotha as the centre of the world⁴². The stepped foot is often identified as the Hill of Golgotha, the place of the crucifixion, which, according to pilgrim's reports, could be reached by steps⁴³. It can, however, also be a representation of

tine ordered the demolition of a pagan temple in the city centre. Under the temple, the hill of Golgotha and Christ's tomb were found whereupon he had two churches built. Connected to this narrative is the story of the Finding of the True Cross by his mother, the empress Helena (Grypeou/Spurling 2013, 73-74, with literature; on Constantine's Church of the Holy Sepulchre and later additions, see Wilkinson 2002, 361-368; Wilkinson/Hill/Ryan 1988, 33-38). Kitzinger (2019, 49-50) sees this knob or *nodus* as a utilitarian element of processional crosses, as a counterweight to keep the balance, and copied in images as such. See also Cotsonis 1994, 112-113.

⁴³ Dinkler/Dinkler-von Schubert 1991, 29, 47-48 and Galavaris 1991, 229. Milner (1996, 94-95) emphasizes that

an actual cross base, used for crosses set up in churches or monumental crosses in a public space⁴⁴. The foot of the cross in Wadi es-Sebua, with an irregular stepped outline and a doorway, is unique in this respect⁴⁵. The latter base might also refer to Golgotha with an elaborate door to an interior space. According to Jerusalem pilgrim's reports, there was a chapel in the rock of Golgotha, which is alternately called the place where Adam was buried⁴⁶, a chapel where masses were said for the dead⁴⁷, or a chapel dedicated to the Holy Blood of Christ that dripped through the fissure in the rock⁴⁸.

The twigs at the end of the cross arms, radiating from the intersection of the cross beams, and flowering branches or on either side of the base (Catalogue – nos 2-3, 11-12, 14) fit in the tradition of the cross seen as the Tree of Life in the garden of Eden. Paradisiacal imagery, water, flowers, fruit, birds, and animals are often part of cross compositions⁴⁹. Rays of light radiating from the intersection of the cross beams refer to the cross as a symbol of light: Christ as the Light of the World (John 8:12)⁵⁰. As the layers of meaning (heavenly Jerusalem, paradise, salvation of death) overlap, cross compositions often blend the features of various themes⁵¹. The Nubian crosses are no exception.

A considerable number of painted (gemmed) crosses in Egypt are standing on a tang. These crosses reflect processional or ceremonial crosses, which would be mounted atop a staff or set in a base. Sometimes the base is also pictured⁵². The group of Nubian crosses discussed here has an extra element: a spike or spearhead under the base – a sharp instrument that can spear a head. Adam's head?

THE CRUCIFIXION AND THE SKULL

According to the Gospels of Matthew (27:33), Mark (15:22), and John (19:17), Christ was killed at the Hill of Golgotha, 'the place of a skull'. As early as the third century, Origen stated that Adam was buried at Golgotha (and refers to 1 Corinthians 15:22). Apocryphal works, written and/or come down to us in Greek, Syriac, or Coptic such as the *Testament of Solomon*, *Cave of Treasures* and the *Life of Adam and Eve* elaborate on the subject. Jerome (d. 420) explained that "... the second Adam, that is the blood of Christ, as it dropped from the cross, washed away the sins of the buried protoplast, the

first Adam..."⁵³. Hereby, Christ had redeemed mankind. In the visual arts of the Eastern Mediterranean, the skull of Adam was often depicted at the foot of the Cross or in a small cave or hollow under the Cross from the ninth century onwards. Often, blood dripping from Christ's wounds would wet the skull⁵⁴.

these pilgrims (Theodosius, ca. 518 and the Piacenza Pilgrim ca. 570: Wilkinson 2002, 107, 139) only mention steps to the place where Christ was crucified, not a monumental cross erected there. Later pilgrims also mention steps: Theodoric (second half twelfth century; Wilkinson/Hill/Ryan 1988, 285). Spalding-Stracey (2020, 109) sees the identification of a stepped base as Golgotha as a Western tradition.

⁴⁴ Innemée/Zielińska 2018, 618-619, 621; Spalding-Stracey 2020, 109.

⁴⁵ Cross bases shaped as a building are rare in wall painting, but a good example can be found in Room 80 of the workshop area of the Monastery of Anba Hadra near Aswan (unpublished). For eleventh-twelfth century Byzantine metal architectonic cross bases representing churches, see, for example, Cotsonis 1994, 108-111 and Catalogue Princeton 2010, 260-271 (S. Ćurčić and B. Ratliff).

⁴⁶ For example, Epiphanius the Monk (seventh century; Wilkinson 2002, 208) and Daniel the Abbot (beginning twelfth century; Wilkinson/Hill/Ryan 1988, 129). For the lay-out of this chapel, see Wilkinson/Hill/Ryan 1988, 36, Fig. 5.

⁴⁷ For example, Adomnan (seventh century) and Bede (beginning eighth century; Wilkinson 2002, 173, 218).

⁴⁸ For example, John of Würzburg and Theodoric (end twelfth century; Wilkinson/Hill/Ryan 1988, 259, 286).

⁴⁹ Schiller 1968, 145; Dinkler/Dinkler-von Schubert 1991, 29-30; Jensen 2017, 29-31 and 131.

⁵⁰ Dinkler/Dinkler-von Schubert 1991, 30.

⁵¹ Dinkler/Dinkler-von Schubert 1991, 29.

⁵² See, for example, the crosses in the so-called Tomb of Shenoute near the White Monastery and the curtain now in Minneapolis (notes 32-33). Most of the crosses in Kellia belong to this type. See also Spalding-Stracey 2020, 100, 105, 185.

⁵³ Bagatti 1977; Montesano 2013; Grypeou/Spurling 2013, 71-79 for an overview of commentaries of the Church Fathers. Quote of Jerome from his *Letter 46*, to Marcella (dated 386); translation in Grypeou/Spurling 2013, 77. Jerome later changed his view and declared that Adam was buried at Hebron (van der Horst 2007; Grypeou/Spurling 2013, 77-79).

⁵⁴ Early examples: the Beresford Hope Cross, probably from Italy, ninth century, London, Victoria & Albert Museum, inv.no. 265&A-1886 (<http://collections.vam.ac.uk/item/O115274/beresford-hope-cross-cross-unknown/>, accessed 20 December 2022); Bagatti 1977, 11 and Jensen 2017, 91). A reliquary cross from Palestine is often quoted as dating to the sixth century but is now dated to ca. 800-1000 (Providence RI, Rhode Island School of Design Museum, inv. no. 51.597, <https://risdmuseum.org/art-design/collection/reliquary-cross-51597>, accessed 20 December 2022); Frazer 1974, 155; Bagatti 1977, 9-10; Montesano 2013, 22).

⁵⁵ Deposition from the cross, Harrowing of Hell, Entombment, Three Marys, Mary Magdalene and an apostle at the Sepulchre, Christ and the doubting Thomas, Appearance of Christ to the disciples, Appearance of Christ to Mary Magdalene (*Noli me tangere*). South aisle, east wall, and south-east corner (Khartoum, Sudan National Museum, inv. no. 24335 and Warsaw, National Museum, inv. no. 234054 MNW; Michałowski 1967, 134-137, Pls 54-56; Jakobielski *et al.* 2017, cat. 90-90A).

⁵⁶ In the *History of the Patriarchs*, the part chronicling the patriarchate of Michael I (744-768), written by a contemporary, describes a Crucifixion scene, which was painted on the wall of the Church of our Lady Mary in Alexandria: "... the Lord Christ on the cross and the one with the spear who was piercing him." The mural was painted high on the wall because the Muslim blasphemer "... ascended to the upper gallery, and stabbed the picture..." (*HPC* III, 149 [403]; Swanson 2006, 240-241, quote on p. 241).

⁵⁷ In Karm al-Ahbariya, a series of the Life of Christ ran around the nave, above the colonnade separating nave and aisles. Two small fragments of feet and torso might point to a crucifixion scene (Witte-Orr 2010, 63 and Pl. 21d). In the Church of the Virgin, a series of the Life of Christ was painted in the nave, above the piers of the south and north wall. Unfortunately, the part between the Entry into Jerusalem and Pentecost (north wall) is almost entirely missing. Above the northern central pier, a small fragment of a covered head with knitted eyebrows was identified by Mat Immerzeel as the head of the mourning Virgin, which could have been part of a Crucifixion scene (Pasi 2010, 45-48; Gabra/van Loon 2012, 64 and 69; Immerzeel 2017, 34 and Figs 5, 8-9). Mark Swanson (2006) explores the apologetic discussion between Egyptian Christians and Muslims on the crucifixion of Christ in the second half of the eighth century. Christ's death on the cross is central to the Christian faith while the Qur'an denies that Christ actually died on the cross. Whether or not this polemic has played a role in the choices made for pictorial programmes remains to be investigated.

⁵⁸ Bibliothèque de Fels, Ms. Copte-Arabe 1, fol. 57r. Likewise, the skull is present in the Deposition from the Cross (<https://bibliotheque.numerique.icp.fr/records/item/4790-evangeliaire-copte-arabe?offset=1>, accessed 20 December 2022).

⁵⁹ Hunt 1985, 134-136, 141-144. There is a small corpus of crucifixion scenes in various media without a skull under the cross, for example, a drawing in a magical papyrus, seventh century (British Library Or. 6796: Sanzo 2015); an embroidery of the crucified Christ on a liturgical stole, an *omophorion* (probably from Akhmim: Berlin, Bodemuseum, SMB-SPK, SMBK, inv. No. 9185. This has a ¹⁴C date of 819-1016 A.D. (95.4%) for the linen ground of the embroidery (<http://www.smb-digital.de/eMuseumPlus?service=ExternalInterface&module=collection&objectId=1891476&viewType=detailView>, accessed 20 December 2022); a narrative scene with women and soldiers around the three crosses (Matthew 27:52-56) in the so-called Gospel Book from Damietta (1179-1180 A.D., written in Coptic; Paris, BnF, Copte 13, fol. 83v (<https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/btv1b52508833q/f174.item>, accessed 20 December 2022); A large embroidery from Egypt in the Benaki Museum in Athens shows the crucified Christ with on either side six apostles (Athens, Benaki Museum, inv. no. Γ'E 7148, 0.48 × 2.63 m, thirteenth century: https://www.benaki.org/index.php?option=com_collectionitems&view=collectionitem&id=103753&lang=en, accessed 20 December 2022).

In Nubia, Crucifixion scenes are not known up till now. In the sequence of biblical events, the nearest composition is a Deposition from the Cross in Faras Cathedral (late tenth-beginning eleventh centuries), which is the first of a series of episodes that took place after the death of Christ, painted in the south aisle of the church. This particular image, as well as the complete series, is unique in Nubian church decoration⁵⁵. In the Deposition, the cross of Christ is flanked by the crosses of the two robbers and all three crosses have a pointed lower end for planting them in the hill of Golgotha. Exactly under the cross of Christ, part of the plaster had already fallen down at the time of excavation. Therefore, it is impossible to know whether the skull of Adam was part of the composition.

In Egypt, literary sources testify to the existence of Crucifixion scenes in churches⁵⁶ but it does not seem to have been a popular theme. It might have figured in a sixth-century Life of Christ series in the church at Karm al-Ahbariya (to the south-west of Alexandria, near Abu Mina) and in a thirteenth-century series in the Church of the Virgin in Dayr al-Baramus (Wadi an-Natrun). Only small fragments of both paintings are preserved, with no traces of a skull⁵⁷.

A Coptic-Arabic Gospel Book preserved in the Institut Catholique in Paris (1250 A.D.), which was made in Cairo, shows a skull in a small cave in the hill under the cross in the Crucifixion scene in the Gospel of Matthew⁵⁸. These illuminations show Byzantine, Syriac, and Crusader influences⁵⁹.

The church of Yəmṛəhännä Krəstos, ca. 20 km north-east from Lalibela in the Amhara Region (Ethiopia) was built in a cave and its pictorial decoration and woodwork are said to be heavily influenced by Egypt. In the north aisle, on the north wall, a late twelfth century Passion series starts with a Crucifixion. It shows an empty, plain Latin cross with circular terminals at the corners of the end of the horizontal cross beam and the top of the shaft. A wreath hangs behind the top; to the left of the shaft are three large nails, to the right two more. The two crucified thieves are painted farther left and right. The cross is planted in a head, laying on its right side. The head has long hair, features, moustache, and a pointed beard: it is almost a copy of the heads under the Nubian crosses. This composition is unique in Ethiopian art and has no parallel in Egypt. As Ewa Balicka-Witakowska points out, a cross without the crucified Christ but crowned

with a lamb as his symbol, flanked by the thieves, is a common scheme in thirteenth-fourteenth century Ethiopian miniatures⁶⁰. The skull of Adam is never part of these compositions.

In Western art, the skull detail appeared somewhat later, from ca. the eleventh century onwards, as one of several motifs indicating the redemption of mankind⁶¹. There is, however, a very interesting Crucifixion scene in a late ninth-early/tenth-century gospel manuscript in Angers (Bibliothèque municipale, Ms. 24), which was most probably copied and illuminated in the Breton/Loire area in north-western France. On fol. 7v, the Crucifixion is depicted, followed, on fol. 8r, by the Deposition from the Cross and the Entombment. In the Crucifixion, the Cross, with Christ on it, is embedded in the Hill of Golgotha, into a head that lies on its side inside the hill. The eyes of the head are closed, he has long hair and a two-pointed beard. Out of this head a snake crawls upwards to the feet of Christ⁶².

Curiously, the head under the Cross has no name while all persons in this miniature are named, including the personifications of sun and moon. Beatrice Kitzinger identifies the head as the head of Adam and in support of this identification, she points to traces of red (blood of Christ) on the head and the resemblance of the faces of Christ and Adam⁶³. The serpent coiled at the foot of the Cross, wrapped around its shaft or raises itself in front of it, is a common feature in Western Crucifixion scenes from the ninth century onwards. It is reminiscent of the serpent in the Garden of Eden that caused the Fall of Man, which is redeemed by Christ's sacrifice: "... the Wood which undid the curse of the tree..."⁶⁴.

THE HEAD

In the Nubian cross designs, the head with its white hair and white beard is obviously slain and defeated under the foot of the Cross. The image reminds us of the age-old iconography of enemies trampled under the feet of a victorious king, pharaoh or emperor, well known in the entire Near-Eastern and Mediterranean world⁶⁵, and the immensely popular equestrian saints conquering foes that could be seen in almost every church. In the Bible, enemies were trampled upon (Is. 63:3) or were made a footstool (for example Ps. 110:1; Mt. 22:44; Mk 12:36; Lk 20:43; Acts 2:35; Hebr. 1:13 and 10:13). Impaling decapitated heads of defeated

adversaries on lances or spears as a sign of victory also has a long history⁶⁶. However, these heads are

⁶⁰ See for photographs <http://ethiopia.deeds.utoronto.ca/> (accessed 20 December 2022), photo numbers: MG-2007.218.051, MG-2007.047.007 and 008. A comprehensive study on this church will be published in the near future (Balicka-Witakowska/Gervers, forthcoming). See for the miniatures Balicka-Witakowska 1997. With many thanks to Ewa Balicka-Witakowska for sharing her unpublished material.

⁶¹ Schiller 1968, 142. As far as in the eleventh-twelfth centuries, Western pilgrims to Jerusalem were not united in seeing the location of the grave of Adam under the cross. Some report of the fissure or crack in which Christ's blood flowed without mentioning the skull or tomb of Adam or they leave him out of their account altogether since he is supposed to be buried at Hebron. See, for example pilgrims' guides or reports in Wilkinson/Hill/Ryan 1988.

⁶² Kitzinger 2019, 176-177, Fig. 139. For the images, see also <https://bvmm.irht.cnrs.fr/iiif/9032/canvas/canvas-1274701/view,images22-32> (accessed 20 December 2022).

⁶³ Kitzinger 2019, 183-184. Kitzinger (2019, 270, note 10, with bibliography) assembled some Western examples with a head under the cross and she points out that these heads are depicted standing. Most of these are not convincing. The two late eighth-early ninth-century north Italian examples preserved in Cividale (Museo diocesano cristiano e del tesoro del duomo and Museo archeologico nazionale di Cividale del Friuli), a reliquary and a small bronze cross, stand in the tradition of small pectoral or reliquary crosses, which became widespread in the ninth-eleventh century Byzantine world. Medallions holding busts of saints and/or the Virgin are depicted at the ends of the shaft and the cross arms (Pitarakis 2006). Furthermore: the Beresford Hope cross (see note 54), ivories in Berlin and Paris originating from northern Italy, show under the cross a kind of mask without hair or beard. These masks can also be found in Byzantine examples and represent simplified skulls (e.g., Schiller 1968, Figs 336-337, 340, 342). Only in the Crucifixion miniature in the eleventh-century Ripoll Bible in the Vatican Library (Vat. Lat. 5729, fol. 369v, Schiller 1968, Fig. 391) does a head with a neck, features, hair, and beard appear standing under the cross.

⁶⁴ Schiller 1968, 124, with examples. Quote: Sophronius of Jerusalem (d. 638), *Anacreonticon* 20, 29 (Wilkinson 2002, 158). Schiller adheres to the typos/antitypos Fall/Salvation but she claims that the snake is often stabbed by the cross. Kitzinger adds that the pointed lower end of the cross (for planting it in the ground; a 'thorned cross') emphasizes the cross as conqueror of death and the devil, personified by the snake (Kitzinger 2019, 47). However, in all Schiller's examples the coiled or crawling snake is very much alive and mostly looks up to Christ. Nor is the cross in these examples always a 'thorned cross'. In my view, both details support the Fall/Salvation idea. See also Kitzinger 2019, 224, note 47.

⁶⁵ Keel 1977, 230-233; Kartsonis 1986, 72-73; Skrzyziar 2002, 91-95, Figs 32-33, 35, 39-41.

⁶⁶ Grotowski 2010, 74-123, 229-333. As an example, Grotowski points to the Chronicle of John Skylitzes where the impaled head of a defeated adversary is presented to

shown fixed upon the shaft in a vertical position contrary to the position of the head under the Nubian crosses.

The crosses refer to the instrument of Christ's final sufferings and at the same time, by their precious decoration, to the glory of his resurrection. Whereas the gospels are not very informative about what happened between Christ's death and resurrection, as early as the second century Church Fathers elaborated on a journey of Christ into the underworld, the abode under the earth where Adam and the Righteous awaited their liberation. In the Greek Bible, this place was called 'Hades' after the ancient Greek god of the dead and king of the underworld⁶⁷. In treatises, sermons, and hymns, Christ's descent into the underworld is told, the defeat of the evil forces who controlled this realm, and the raising of Adam and the Righteous. The stories are often very lively and narrated with much

detail. The evil forces of the netherworld are designated in the texts as Hades, Satan, the devil or demon, Tyrant, and Serpent (who seduced Eve in the Garden of Eden). Satan and the serpent conspired with Hades and sometimes the sons of Satan would join the troupe. 'Hades' is considered, at the same time, as a toponym and as an acting creature⁶⁸. These legends and tales on the so-called Anastasis, literally the Resurrection, had been incorporated in the Creed and the liturgy by the fourth century⁶⁹.

An early surviving image of Christ descending into the underworld can be found on one of the ciborium columns of the main altar in San Marco in Venice, which were most probably made in an imperial workshop, in Constantinople or elsewhere in the empire, around 500-525. Christ treads on the heads of Hades, depicted as a Greek god, and Satan, depicted as a monster⁷⁰. The earliest wall paintings, in Santa Maria Antiqua in Rome, date to the beginning of the eighth century and show Christ trampling on a dark-skinned demonic figure. He takes Adam by the hand while he holds a scroll in his left hand⁷¹. 'Evil' is often represented by dragons, serpents, monsters, and demons⁷². Hades could be portrayed in different guises, following the various stories, legends, and traditions around this theme, but he could also retain his classical features as a Greek god with long, somewhat tousled hair and a beard⁷³ as in the San Marco column. In visual arts, some of the evil forces of the netherworld can be represented but mostly one of them embodied all, thereby personifying the underlying meaning: death⁷⁴.

In late ninth-century Western examples of the Anastasis scene Christ carries a cross staff, thereby showing that the deliverance of the dead was possible through his suffering. However, whether this element originated in the West or the East is not clear⁷⁵. The cross staff has become a weapon with a spear head in a group of tenth- or eleventh-century (south-)Italian Exultet rolls (a rolled manuscript with hymns to be sung at the Easter Vigil): Christ stands on a prostrate anthropomorphic figure whose left cheek he touches with the blade of his cross staff or Christ attacks the prostrate figure by driving the cross staff-spear through his mouth⁷⁶. In both miniatures, the light skinned figure with long hair and a beard represents Hades. A mosaic in the church of Daphni Monastery (near Athens) shows Christ planting his cross staff (without spear

the ruler (Madrid, Biblioteca Nacional, inv. no. Vitr. 26-2, fol. 224v. Provenance: Palermo; <http://bdh-rd.bne.es/viewer.vm?id=0000022766&page=1>, image 458, accessed 20 December 2022).

⁶⁷ 'Hades' is translated from the Hebrew *sheol*, a similar place for departed souls in the Jewish tradition and in the Old Testament (Somov 2020).

⁶⁸ Ephraim the Syrian, the fourth-century Church Father and poet, designates the underworld as *sheol*, albeit with the same double connotation of toponym and personification. For Ephraim's hymns on this subject, see Frank 2010, 62-65.

⁶⁹ Frazer 1974, 157-161; Kartsonis 1986, 29-30, 69-70; Weigel 1997, 258-263; Frank 2009 and 2010, who points out that these stories have their roots in Graeco-Roman myth and early Jewish apocalypses. See also Innemée/Zielińska 2019, 138-139.

⁷⁰ Ciborium column D, zone 7 (Weigel 1997, 283, on the date, see 254-255). The date of these columns has been disputed for a long time, also see Żurawski 2007, 176-177.

⁷¹ Kartsonis 1986, 29-30, 69-70 and Figs 14a-b, 15 (Rome, Santa Maria Antiqua, and the lost paintings from the Oratory of John VII in Old St Peter's basilica).

⁷² See Innemée/Zielińska 2019 for the Nubian tradition.

⁷³ Maguire 2018. See examples in Skrzyniarz 2002, 80-91, Figs 19-21, 25-27.

⁷⁴ Kartsonis 1986, 73-74.

⁷⁵ Kartsonis 1986, 85-86.

⁷⁶ Kartsonis 1986, 85-87. Exultet rolls: Manchester, John Rylands Library, Latin Ms. 2, second skin (<https://luna.manchester.ac.uk/luna/servlet/detail/Man4MedievalVC-4-4-994347-230019>, accessed 20 December 2022) and Velletri (Frazer 1974, Fig. 8). In a third Exultet illumination, Christ drives his spear with a small cross above the spear head in the neck of a dark-skinned demon (Vatican, Vatican Library, Cod. Lat. 9820: Kartsonis 1986, Fig. 20a).

head) on the neck of a light skinned man with beard and long hair⁷⁷.

Two Anastasis scenes have been found in Nubia up till now, both dating to the tenth- eleventh centuries⁷⁸. The painting in Faras Cathedral (see above) shows Christ trampling on a dark-skinned prostrate figure. He holds a cross staff in his left hand. To the left writhes a serpent. The dark-skinned figure is alternatively identified as Hades or Satan⁷⁹. In the Lower Church of Banganarti, further south near Old-Dongola, Christ tramples a light skinned figure, Hades, stretched below his feet. According to Bogdan Żurawski, Christ holds a 'crossed lance (?)' in his left hand while he raises Adam with his right hand⁸⁰. The head of Hades is no longer visible but regarding the position of the staff/lance in the reconstruction drawing, it is very well possible that Hades is being stabbed in the head.

This particular type of the Anastasis iconography, Christ's cross staff-spear stabbing the head of Hades is, in my view, related to the triumphal crosses in Nubian churches. The head under these crosses has the classical features of the god of the underworld with long dishevelled hair and a beard. The cross staff has become an independent sign, a victorious, glorious cross representing the Resurrection and the Second Coming of Christ, that vanquishes Hades, the personification of death.

In a pascal homily, attributed to Hesychius of Jerusalem (fifth century), Christ has trampled death under his feet, imprisoned the tyrant and wrecked Hades⁸¹. The good thief in Romanos the Melodist's *kontakion On the Adoration of the Cross* (sixth century) says: "Thou art the terrible spear striking the power of demons..."⁸². The *Stauros*-hymns stress that the Cross is the victory over the Devil and the destruction of all evil.

Why only the head as a *pars pro toto* is depicted, might simply have to do with compositional reasons, or it might have to do with an allusion to the skull of Adam. Although this feature, as far as is known, does not occur in Nubian visual art and the stories around Adam's tomb are, up till now, not attested in Nubia, it is likely that they were known. Jerusalem, the Holy City, was the most prominent pilgrimage goal of the Christian world and as such, cannot have failed to attract Nubian Christians. As Adam Simmons states, this evidence is meagre before the twelfth century but "... identifying Nubians in the Holy Land during the first

millennium is largely a problem of the identification of toponyms and ethnonyms..."⁸³.

Whether the inscription 'Adam' just below the foot of the cross in Faras Cathedral (Catalogue – no. 3; Pl. 3) belongs to the stabbed head is not entirely clear. In my view, it is written a bit too far from the head and it might point to the base of the cross as Golgotha and the stories around this holy site.

The heads in the illumination in the Angers Gospels and in the painting in the church of Yəmrəḥannā Krəstos are, in my view, not the head of Adam: They belong to the Hades iconography. The Hades-head and the wreath hanging from top of the cross in the Yəmrəḥannā Krəstos painting, emphasize the significance of the empty cross as the Triumphant Cross, victory over death and evil⁸⁴. In the Angers miniature, the cross is lodged in the head. The serpent, which caused the fall of men, crawls upwards from this place, Hades the underworld, which

⁷⁷ Kartsonis 1986, Fig. 85; Maguire 2018, Fig. 15.2. Spear- ing evil creatures through the head is one possibility; they can also be speared in the stomach.

⁷⁸ Stories of Christ's descent into the underworld are preserved in Coptic, for example in *The Book of the Resurrection of Jesus Christ* (Frank 2009, 219). A few images, which show Byzantine influence, are known in Egypt: for example, a panel from the wooden doors of the Hanging Church in Old Cairo (London, British Museum, inv. no. 1878,1203.4, mid-thirteenth century (https://www.british-museum.org/collection/object/H_1878-1203-4, accessed 20 December 2022); Immerzeel 2017, 75-76), a screen icon with the seven major feasts in the Church of the Virgin at Haret Zuwayla in Cairo (Skálová in Skálová/Gabra 2006, 200-207: ca. 1200; Gabra/van Loon 2012, 136-137; Immerzeel 2017, 86-89: ca. 1300; see also Mat Immerzeel's contribution to this volume, p. 45, 48), an icon in Dayr as-Suryan, thirteenth century (Skálová in Skálová/Gabra 2006, Fig. III.35). In these compositions, Christ raises Adam (and Eve) from his (their) tomb(s). In the wooden panel, two angels capture a prostrate underworld figure with the features of Hades, long wild hair, and a beard; the icons show shattered gates.

⁷⁹ Hades: Dinkler 1975, 23-24; Vantini 1990, 658; Innemée/Zielińska 2019, 139. Satan: Jakobielski *et al.* 2017, 296.

⁸⁰ Żurawski 2007, 167-169, Figs 7-8, although later, he expresses doubts (pp. 180-181).

⁸¹ *Pascal Homily I* (Aubineau 1972, 68-69). The text is known from a ninth-century manuscript (Sinai, Monastery of St. Catherine, Cod. Sin. Gr. 492; Aubineau 1972, 42-43, 47). Aubineau (1972, 97-99) points to similar expressions in Church Fathers' writings.

⁸² Trans. Carpenter 1970, 244.

⁸³ Simmons 2019, 27-28.

⁸⁴ Balicka-Witakowska in Balicka-Witakowska/Gervers, forthcoming.

is his abode as Romanos the Melodist wrote in his *kontakion* mentioned above⁸⁵.

Christ's Blood dripping on this Hades-head might be an association with the head of Adam. Both traditions were known, as the priest John of Würzburg, who made a pilgrimage to the Holy Land during the years 1160-1170, testifies. In his detailed description of the 'Place of a Skull' he noted that:

(...) the stone on which the Cross had been fixed, in the very part which had been touched by his blood, was cracked in the middle. Through this crack his blood flowed down to a place below, where certain people say that Adam had been buried, and he was thus baptized in the Blood of Christ. To make this point more clear they say that everywhere a dead skull is painted at the feet of the crucified one. But Adam being 'baptized in the blood of Christ' means nothing more than that he is 'redeemed by the blood of Christ', because Scripture tells us that Adam was buried in Hebron. And the ugly face of a man which people used to paint underneath the feet of the crucified one rather means Death and the destruction of Death: this why the Lord says, 'O Death, I will be your death', (Hosea 13:14) that is, your destruction⁸⁶.

The cross in the church in the temple of Wadi es-Sebua (Catalogue – no. 11; Pl. 13) is, as stated

above, an original composition. The base of the cross, an irregular 'hill' most probably represents Golgotha. The doorway in the base demonstrates knowledge of the holy place: according to pilgrims' accounts there was a chapel in the rock. There is no spike and compared to the careful and precise painting of the cross, the head looks out of place, in style as well as in the overall composition. It might have been a later addition. Nevertheless, like the head in the crucifixion scenes in the Angers gospels, it shows that stories and pictorial traditions can overlap, although this time it is the other way round: It is reminiscent of Adam but with the features of Hades.

The composition of the Nubian triumphal crosses impaling the head of Hades is a distinctive and original form in Nubian iconography. At the same time, elements of this composition are embedded in the contemporary theological, liturgical, literary, cultural, and social Mediterranean world. Contacts between Nubia and Ethiopia, both Christian kingdoms under ecclesiastical leadership of the Coptic patriarchate of Alexandria, no doubt existed although not much is known⁸⁷. Whether there might be a connection between the Angers gospels and Nubia, is the matter for a different investigation⁸⁸.

CONCLUSION: THE POWER OF THE CROSS

The importance of the Cross as a symbol of life over death, cannot be overestimated. A Sahidic manuscript in the British Library contains a homily attributed to Cyril of Jerusalem entitled *On the Appearance of the Cross*. It was copied in 1053 or 1056 for a Nubian patron from Faras as a gift to the Church of the Cross near Serra, to the south of Faras⁸⁹. The theme of the homily was, according to Jacques van der Vliet, "... aptly chosen to support the local veneration of the Holy Cross". Two roughly contemporary manuscripts were destined for a Jesus Church in Serra-East, donated by different families. One contained a Cross hymn and the other, the so-called Serra-East Codex, a homily on the Holy Cross, Ps. Chrysostom's *In venerabilem crucem sermo* (which incorporates a *Stauros*-hymn). Recent investigations have shown that this story had a long history in Nubia. According to the colophon, the latter manuscript was "... placed upon the cross resting in the Jesus (church) at Serra East"⁹⁰. In the *Stauros*-hymn, writing praise on the cross and donating such a book to the church is set

⁸⁵ Trans. Carpenter 1970, 230-238.

⁸⁶ Wilkinson/Hill/Ryan 1988, 21, 258-259.

⁸⁷ Loiseau 2019, 1-2.

⁸⁸ Żurawski (2007, 168-182) suspects Western inspiration for the unusual composition of the Anastasis in the Lower Church of Banganarti. At present, there is no earlier direct evidence for Western connections than the second half of the thirteenth-fourteenth centuries when a certain Benedictus from the Provence left his name in the Upper Church of Banganarti (Łajtar/Płóciennik 2011). Knowledge on Christian Nubia in the West is attested from around the twelfth century onwards. Pilgrims met Nubians in Jerusalem (for example, the pilgrimage account of Theodoric, 1168-1174: Wilkinson/Hill/Ryan 1988, 282); merchants and diplomats met them in Egypt and Christian Nubia appeared as a country on maps (Łajtar/Płóciennik 2011, 110-118; Seignobos 2014). However, as stated above, it is almost certain that contacts in Jerusalem must have existed at an earlier stage.

⁸⁹ BL Or. 6799 (Layton 1987, 89-90, no. 83); van der Vliet 2015, 273.

⁹⁰ Browne 1983, 98 (Berlin, Staatsbibliothek, Ms. Or. Quart. 1020, tenth-eleventh centuries – DBMNT 1391); van Gerven Oei/Tsakos 2020, 211-212 (Khartoum, SNM, eleventh-twelfth centuries – DBMNT 1385).

on one line with works of mercy such as feeding the hungry or clothing the naked⁹¹.

Old Dongola, the capital of Makuria, had a ninth-century cruciform church. In his description and reconstruction of this church, Włodzimierz Godlewski suggests that a lofty ciborium in the heart of the building could have sheltered a large cross of precious metal⁹².

Unfortunately, such crosses, processional or as reliquaries, have not been found in Nubia. There are, however, literary witnesses. Egyptian historians an-Nuwayrī (d. 1333 A.D.) and Ibn al-Furāt (d. 1405 A.D.), recorded that during the invasion in Nubia by the Mamluk sultan al-Zāhir Rukn al-Dīn Baybars, the Church of Sūs or Isūs (Jesus) in Old Dongola (unidentified) was destroyed in 1276 A.D. and "... crosses, gold and other objects ... and silver vases..." (an-Nuwayrī) or "... golden crosses and other objects..." (Ibn al-Furāt) were taken as booty⁹³.

Feasts dedicated to the Holy Cross were celebrated in Jerusalem since the fourth century and in Constantinople since the sixth century⁹⁴. In Egypt, the Feast of the Holy Cross (17 Thoth/14 September) was an important and established feast since at least the beginning of the seventh century⁹⁵. The Nubian synaxarion and the liturgical calendar are still not very well known, which is predominantly due to a lack of sources. Preliminary investigations of the limited corpus of lectionary fragments preserved suggest that Nubian Christians developed their own system of readings. Based on a pattern of the most important liturgical feasts (imported with the introduction of Christianity), they added local saints and feasts. Egypt was, in this respect, a most likely source of influence⁹⁶. It is almost certain that, following Christian Egypt, Byzantium and Jerusalem (and in the light of the popularity of cross imagery in word and image), feasts dedicated to the Holy Cross figured on their calendar and likewise, these and other feasts were celebrated with processions in which crosses were carried around.

The elaborate (processional) crosses preserved in Egypt and the Mediterranean world (which might also function as reliquaries) were very often gifted to churches and monasteries by pious donors⁹⁷. So were in Nubia the written works mentioned above and so were the painted crosses in churches, as the inscriptions and figures of donors accompanying the crosses show. However, these murals do not occupy a 'liturgical' location: they are not painted

in altar rooms or in settings that are reminiscent of liturgical ceremonies. They are mainly found in side-aisles and side rooms of church buildings. In praise of the Glorious Cross, these wall paintings were offered by private individuals, who expressed their hope for protection, help, and the salvation of their soul.

The epitaphs of a large number of stelae, found all over the Middle Nile Valley from Nobadia to Alwa, start with the invocation "God of the spirits and of all flesh, you who defeated death and trodden down Hades and given life to the world..."⁹⁸. It is this belief that the donors testified to in selecting a representation of the Cross as their gift.

The crosses refer to the Crucifixion, Christ's suffering and death, his sacrifice for mankind, as related in the gospels. At the same time, they signify victory and the future: the *Parousia*, the Second Coming of Christ at the end of times, the Heavenly

⁹¹ Browne 1983, 87-88. In the *Stauros*-hymn in the Qasr al-Wizz codex (Aswan, Nubia Museum, inv. no. 168, ninth century? – DBMNT 1753), only the writing of praise of the Cross is mentioned in this context (Tsakos *et al.* 2013, 201-202). The works of mercy (feeding the hungry, giving water to the thirsty, clothing the naked, caring for the sick, visiting the prisoners) are mentioned in Matthew 25:35-45, the teaching on the Final Judgement.

⁹² Godlewski 2013, 39-41. See also Innemée/Zielińska 2018, 622.

⁹³ Vantini 1975, 467, 472, 475, 528, 534 and 536. See also Godlewski 2013, 41 and Innemée/Zielińska 2018, 622.

⁹⁴ Dinkler/Dinkler-von Schubert 1991, 19-20. For Cross feasts in Constantinople, see Cotsonis 1994, 24-29 and Flusin 2019.

⁹⁵ Personal communication Jacques van der Vliet, many thanks for this. For an eighth-century mention, see note 25.

⁹⁶ Ochała 2015; Łajtar/Rizos 2020.

⁹⁷ In Egypt, see, for example, the silver cross made for a monastery of Apa Shenoute, sixth-seventh centuries (Coquin/Leroy/van Moorsel 1989; Severin 1995). Byzantine votive crosses: Cotsonis 1994, 29-32.

⁹⁸ These epitaphs contain a prayer for the dead that was, quite early, widely known in the Eastern Mediterranean. Up till now, the first attestation of this prayer goes back to an early seventh-century papyrus discovered in Nessana (Tel Nit-zana, South-west Palestine, near the present Egyptian border). The expression 'trodden down Hades' is found in Nubia (and perhaps in the Nessana papyrus: Łajtar 1997, 112); the Byzantine version reads 'diabolon', 'trodden down the devil' (Brakmann 2006, 306). The prayer might have originated in a Syriac-Palestinian milieu, from where it found its way to Nubia via Egypt. It is, thus far, not attested in Nubian liturgy but only on stelae. The tombstones in question date to the eight-thirteenth centuries (Łajtar 1997 and 2003, XXI-XXIII; Brakmann 2006, 300-310. See also Innemée/Zielińska 2019, 139-140).

Jerusalem and Paradise, a place where death will be no more. On a human level, the imposing and rich crosses impaling Hades express the donor's hope and faith in her or his share in the world to come in which the victorious Christ through His Cross had crushed and destroyed the last enemy⁹⁹.

CATALOGUE

A. Crosses spearing a head

1. Sonqi Tino, church, soffit of arch between nave and north aisle (next to pulpit), eastern part (Pl. 1). Date: end ninth-beginning eleventh centuries? (Pasi); second half tenth century-turn of tenth-eleventh century (Zielińska).

Size: 52 cm wide and 101 cm high (fragment preserved).

Present location: Khartoum, Sudan National Museum, inv. no. 32156.

Description: A light-coloured Latin cross with straight arms, which have a small transverse beam at the end. The cross beams are decorated with painted red and light-coloured round and diamond-shaped gemstones. Chains with hanging objects, presumably bells, close the upper quarters. A red *velum* is draped over the horizontal cross beam, hanging in front of the cross with the end falling down from behind.

A short spike under the lower transverse beam points to a head which lies on its left side and is drawn in brown red. Eyes, mouth and beard are still discernible.

Inscriptions: during a later phase, a Greek text was written partly over the cross. Unpublished.

Literature: Donadoni 1997, 382; Pasi 2012: 575-576; Zielińska 2012, 593.

⁹⁹ With many thanks to Paul Barford (Warsaw) for correcting my English and to the Sudan National Museum (Khartoum), the National Museum Warsaw, the Polish Centre of Mediterranean Archaeology/University of Warsaw, the Istituto Nazionale di Archeologia e Storia dell'Arte (Rome), Sapienza Università di Roma, Chair of Egyptology, and the Rijksmuseum van Oudheden (Leiden) for permission to publish photographs.

¹⁰⁰ For this cross as well as the other crosses in Faras Cathedral published in Jakobielski *et al.* 2017, see the extensive bibliography for each entry in this book.

2. Faras, Cathedral, South Chapel, south wall, ca. 50 cm above floor level (Pl. 2).

Date: late tenth century.

Size: ca. 391 cm high; 247 cm wide. Square with Christ ca. 24 cm.

Present location: Khartoum, Sudan National Museum, inv. no. 24310.

Description: Latin cross with slightly flared arms. The ends of the cross bar and the top of the shaft have multiple terminals: lozenge-shaped elements at the corners with a hemispherical decoration in between. From each end sprout three red twigs. The lower end of the shaft has the corner decoration only. The quarters are closed with bell chains. In the intersection of the beams, a bust of Christ, holding a book in his left arm, is painted. Around this square, in the corners of the cross arms, are four squares enclosing the standing Four Living Creatures. The cross rests on a slightly flattened sphere and a four stepped base. Below the base, a spike points down into a head, which lies on its left side.

The yellow ochre cross has red outlines dotted with white drops imitating pearls and it is decorated with alternating red and green painted gemstones. The pierced head under the cross has red outlines. It is slightly elongated and has hair and a pointed beard.

Inscriptions: none.

Literature: Michałowski 1967, 124-125, Pl. 44; Jakobielski *et al.* 2017, cat. 97 (M. Martens-Czarnecka/S. Jakobielski)¹⁰⁰.

3. Faras, Cathedral, north aisle, western part of the soffit of the arch to the northern vestibule (Pl. 3).

Date: early eleventh century.

Size: ca. 168 cm high; 177 cm wide. Medallion with Christ 30 cm high and 25 cm wide.

Present location: Khartoum, Sudan National Museum, inv. no. 24333.

Description: A double cross consisting of a Greek cross with slightly flared arms set on a larger cross of which the shaft is longer than the horizontal beams. Cross and base are painted in yellow ochre with pearl-studded red borders, each pearl filled with a red dot, and densely set with pearls and red and green gemstones in different shapes. The small

Pl. 1. Songi Tino, church (drawing: Dobrochna Zielińska;
 photograph: Sudan National Museum, Khartoum)

Pl. 2. Faras, Cathedral, South Chapel, south wall
 (photograph: Sudan National Museum, Khartoum)

Pl. 3. Faras, Cathedral, north aisle
 (after Michałowski 1967, Pl. 88)

cross has straight cross arms with lozenge-shaped clasps at the corners and carries a large medallion with a bust of Christ, who holds a book in his left arm, on the intersection of the cross beams. The medallion is surrounded by the Four Living Creatures in the quarters, their heads enclosed by wings. The arms and the top of the large cross have lozenge-shaped clasps at the corners with a small hemisphere in between while the lower cross beam (also with clasps) rests on two flattened spherical shapes, which in turn rest on a base consisting of three steps. The base is flanked by three green twigs with red fruit or flowers. Chains with bells are strung between the clasps of the large cross, thereby closing the quarters. Similar bell chains hooked in the centre of the large chains are clasped to the corners of the small cross arms, thus creating a square around the smaller cross. Under the base is a hemisphere with a spike, which pierces a head. The elongated head, fairly well preserved, is lying on its left side and has long white hair, moustache and pointed beard. The eyes have red and yellow shadows.

Inscriptions: Greek. *Stauros*, names of Christ and the Living Creatures, 'Adam' below the foot (right), dedicatory text of a woman ('E..., daughter of Mar...').

Literature: Michałowski 1967, 161-162, Pl. 88 (with head); Jakobielski *et al.* 2017, cat. 77 (S. Jakobielski/M. Martens-Czarnecka).

4. Faras, Cathedral, north aisle, east face of the pilaster of the second north-south arch from the west (next to the western pilaster of the entrance to the northern vestibule (Pl. 4).

Date: eleventh-thirteenth centuries.

Size: 15.5 cm high and 10.5 cm wide.

Present location: Khartoum, Sudan National Museum, inv. no. 24334.

Description: Drawing of a Latin cross with a double outline. A head of Christ in a square is set on the intersection of the cross beams. Near the end of the cross arms and the bottom and top of the shaft, squares contain a nimbed head. The four arms have an ogee-pointed end. In the quarters, the Four Living Creatures are depicted (the upper right-hand corner is damaged). A spike or spearhead under the

cross has impaled a head, lying on its right side. The head has hair and a beard, and the eyebrows are still visible. A *velum*, depicted as a band, goes around the cross and the ends hang down on either side of the head, as if it is knotted between cross and spike.

Inscriptions: none.

Literature: Jakobielski 1972, plan III, no. 39; Ratyński 1982, 270, Fig. 22.

5. Faras, Rivergate Church, west face of addition to the north pillar of the altar room and part of soffit of arch, above the pulpit (Pl. 5).

Date: second half twelfth-fifteenth centuries.

Size: unknown.

Not preserved.

Description: An almost Greek, light coloured plain cross with the arms terminating in trefoils. The cross is outlined with a double line, orange-red and black. On the centre, an orange oval with a bust of Christ is depicted, his right hand in a speaking gesture. In the quarters of the cross are the Four Living Creatures. A red *velum* with some white stripes at the ends rests on the top and is draped on the trefoils of the horizontal beam. Garlands close the lower quarters. The lower trefoil rests on a sphere under which a long spike points down, spearing a head. The head lies on its left side. It is drawn in black, and it has features, white hair, and a white beard. To the right of the spike, a standing priest or bishop, is depicted in white, and red and yellow ochre. He is dressed in liturgical vestments, an ankle long tunic, a *phelonion* and an *epitrachelion*.
Inscriptions: Greek inscription mentioning the priest Goassi or Joassi (to the left of the spike). This might be a secondary visitor's inscription.

Literature: Griffith 1926, 79-80, 92, Pls XLVI, no. 37 (plan), LVI-1 (= Monneret de Villard 1935/1957, vol. IV: Pl. CXLVI-4), LVII (= Monneret de Villard 1935/1957, vol. IV: Pls CXLVII-1), LXV-14 ; Monneret de Villard 1935/1957, vol. I: 195-196; Martens-Czarnecka 1992, 373-376.

6. Tamit, Church of Angels (cruciform church), southern cross aisle, north end of west wall (Pl. 6).

Date: thirteenth-fourteenth centuries (probably the end of this period: Godlewski 1996: 53).

Pl. 4. Faras, Cathedral, north aisle (photograph: Sudan National Museum, Khartoum)

Pl. 5. Faras, Rivergate Church (after Griffith 1926, Pl. LVII)

Pl. 6. Tamit, Church of Angels (cruciform church), southern cross aisle (photograph: Istituto Nazionale di Archeologia e Storia dell'Arte, Rome, Fondo Monneret de Villard, inv. no. 70608)

Size: unknown.
Not preserved.

Description: A Greek cross with slightly flared arms ending in trefoils, quite similar to the cross in the Rivergate Church. It was probably yellow ochre with a double outline (a thin and a thick outline) in a darker colour. On the intersection of the beams is a round/oval shape, most likely a medallion, with a double outline but who or what was depicted in this roundel is no longer visible. A dark coloured (red or purple?) *velum* with a white stripe at the ends is draped over the horizontal cross arms, with the ends falling down from behind. A narrow spike points down into a head with features, hair, and beard, lying on its left side.

Inscriptions: Greek: *stauros* above the cross.

Literature: Monneret de Villard 1935/1957, vol. I, 158, Figs. 141 (no. 30)-142, vol. IV: Pl. CLXV; Baldassarre 1967, 57-58; Godlewski 1996, 53.

B. Cross with spike but no head or fragment of head preserved

7. Tamit, Church of Raphael (or Church of the Shaykh), northern side aisle, north wall (Pls 7-9).
Date: tenth-eleventh centuries.
Size: unknown.
Not preserved.

Description: A double cross, which is reminiscent of the Faras crosses nos 3 and 14 (Pls 3, 16): a Greek cross with slightly flared arms carries a large medallion with a bust of Christ, holding a book in his left arm, surrounded by the heads and wings of the Four Living Creatures in the quarters. The straight cross arms have lozenge-shaped clasps at the corners. This cross is set on a larger cross, of which the shaft is longer than the horizontal beam. All arms have lozenge-shaped clasps at the corners. The horizontal cross arms and the top end in a small hemisphere. The cross rests on three more or less spherical shapes. Chains with bells are strung between the clasps of the large cross, thereby closing the quarters. Similar bell chains hooked in the centre of the large chains are fixed to the corners of the small cross arms, thus creating a square around the smaller cross.

A dark-skinned woman (a donor) is depicted standing to the right of the cross, under the horizontal cross arm and overlapping the bell chains. She wears a voluminous light-coloured long garment with long sleeves. A veil covers her head. In her right hand, she holds a branch, which is split up into three twigs. The colours are not recorded. After this painting had fallen down, a lower level was excavated. In the publication, Baldassarre writes that the hemisphere under the base was apparently the last element, thereby omitting the spike. However, according to an excavation photograph and her notes, a stepped base, outlined in brown-red, with a composite spike below (rectangle, hemisphere, spike) were found (Pls 8-9). These elements were studded with small circles/dots, probably representing pearls or gemstones.

Inscriptions: none.

Monneret de Villard 1935/1957, vol. I: 153 and Figs 139-140 (no. 5), vol. IV: Pl. CLIV; Baldassarre 1964: supporto per la croce della pittura n. 5 del Monneret; Baldassarre 1967: 41-42 and Pl. 14-1.

8. Faras, Cathedral, south aisle, entrance to South Chapel, western pilaster (Pl. 10).

Date: early eleventh century.

Size: ca. 145 cm above floor level, ca. 82 cm high (with inscription).

Present location: Khartoum, Sudan National Museum, inv. no. 24368.

Description: Fragments of the gemmed cross are preserved: the shaft, a vertical foot, and the spike, which is attached to a disk-like element. Some small paint remains show that the quarters of the cross were closed with yellow bell chains fastened on clasps. The cross itself and the foot are yellow with a red, pearl studded borders. It is set with green and red round and square jewels. The disk and spike are grey. During a later phase, the composition was overpainted (Jakobielski *et al.* 2017, 320-321, cat. 135).

Inscriptions: Greek: dedicatory inscription of Bishop Marianos

Literature: Michałowski 1967, 161-162, Pl. 89; Jakobielski *et al.* 2017, cat. 99 (M. Martens-Czarnecka/S. Jakobielski).

Pl. 7. Tamit, Church of Raphael (or Church of the Shaykh), northern side aisle (photograph: Istituto Nazionale di Archeologia e Storia dell'Arte, Rome, Fondo Monneret de Villard, inv. no. 70605)

Pl. 8. Tamit, Church of Raphael (or Church of the Shaykh), northern side aisle. Detail of the foot of the cross (photograph: archive of the Chair of Egyptology, Sapienza Università di Roma)

Pl. 9. Tamit, Church of Raphael (or Church of the Shaykh), northern side aisle. Detail of the foot of the cross, sketch I. Baldassarre (archive of the Chair of Egyptology, Sapienza Università di Roma)

9. Old Dongola, N-W Annex of the Monastery on Kom H, Room 2a, w-wall, central niche (Pl. 11).
Date: first half twelfth century.
Size: (of preserved part) 131 cm high; length horizontal beam ca. 60 cm.
Present location: in situ.

Description: The cross is very fragmentarily preserved. The intersection of the cross beams and the outline of the horizontal beam are faintly visible. The right arm has a transverse end and square clasps for bell chains. The lower part of the cross-shaft rests on a spherical shape, followed by a rectangle, a square standing on a corner and a smaller rectangle, and a spike pointing down to a concave line that might have been a head. Cross and spike are yellow ochre with red outlines and floral and geometrical decoration marked with white dots.

Inscriptions: none.

Literature: Martens-Czarnecka 2011, 57, 238, Fig. 126, accompanying cd: cat. no. 9.

10. Faras, Cathedral, south aisle, wall blocking the entrance to the South Chapel (Pl. 12).
Date: Late thirteenth century or later.
Size: (of the fragment preserved) 125 cm high and 100 cm wide.
Not preserved (not removed from the wall).

Description: The lower half of the painting remained, showing a (Latin?) cross with straight arms. On the horizontal beam are the busts of the Trinity in a square and two rectangular frames, while the enthroned Virgin and Child were depicted on the lower half of the shaft. Half figures of the Four Living Creatures were painted in the quarters, surrounded by wings, with the Lion-headed and Ox-headed Creatures preserved. Under the cross was a long spike and fragments of white lines halfway up the spike perhaps belonged to a head. The cross was yellow ochre and covered with a red lattice pattern. It was outlined in dark red.

Inscriptions: none.

Literature: Jakobielski *et al.* 2017, cat. 152 (B. Rostkowska/S. Jakobielski/M. Martens-Czarnecka).

C. Cross with head under the base but no spike

11. Wadi es-Sebua, Church of the Virgin in the Temple of Ramses II, corridor to the Chapel of St. Peter, northern rock face (Pl. 13).
Date: tenth century or later.
Size: ca. 175 cm high (200 cm with base); ca. 80 cm wide (base: 52 cm wide).
Present location: Cairo, Coptic Museum, inv. no. 11488.

Description: A yellow ochre Latin cross is standing on an irregular stepped foot or base. The cross has straight arms and a red and black outline. Almond shaped elements ornate the corners of the top of the shaft and the ends of the horizontal cross beam. Apart from the intersection of the cross beams, the arms are decorated with round and square gemstones, painted in black and red. From the centre of the cross radiate bundles of three red branches, ending in round shapes of different sizes, each filled with a cross. Red bell chains close the quarters and make up a kind of mandorla around the cross. The irregular base has one step on the left and at least two on the right (a part has been damaged). The outline is double with dots at a regular distance in between. In the centre of the base is a red keyhole shaped opening framed by straight jambs and a lintel.

A head, laying on its left side under the base was painted in red. The head has short hair, rendered in half-circles following the line of the forehead from eye to eye. The eyes seem to be closed. A small standing figure (a donor?) is depicted to the left of the cross, in the lower left-hand quarter.

Inscriptions: none.

Literature: Gauthier 1911, 119, Pl. CXXVII-B; Prussian Expedition 1909 (Beinlich 2018, no. B2004); Johann Georg, Duke of Saxony 1914, 64; Monneret De Villard 1935/1957, vol. I: 87, vol. II, Pl. XL, vol. IV: Pl. CXL-B; Medić 1965, Fig. 19 (Fragment 4); Daumas 1967, 41, Pl. VI-B (with a symmetrical cross base and the head without hair); van Loon *et al.* 2022, 107-108 and Fig. 4.

D. Possible cases

12. Faras, Cathedral, South Chapel, south wall, painted under cross no. 2 (Pl. 14).

Pl. 10. Faras, Cathedral, south aisle
(after Jakobielski et al. 2017, 321)

Pl. 11. Old Dongola, N-W Annex of the Monastery on Kom H, Room 2a (photograph and drawing: Małgorzata Martens-Czarnecka; courtesy of the Polish Centre of Mediterranean Archaeology - University of Warsaw)

Pl. 12. Faras, Cathedral, south aisle
(after Jakobielski et al. 2017, 455)

Pl. 13. Wadi es-Sebua, Church of the Virgin in the temple of Ramses II, corridor to the Chapel of St. Peter
(after Gauthier 1911, Pl. CXXVII-B)

Pl. 14. Faras, Cathedral, South Chapel
(after Jakobielski et al. 2017, 209)

Pl. 15. Abdallah-n Irqi, Central Church, south-eastern part
(photograph: Rijksmuseum van Oudheden, Leiden/
Abdallah'n Irqi 8.2.2b_17a, photo 27)

Pl. 16. Faras, Cathedral, northern vestibule,
west wall (photograph: Adam Oleksiak/NMW;
Collection of the National Museum in Warsaw)

Date: first half tenth century.

Size: identical to no. 2, ca. 391 cm high and 247 cm wide.

Present location: Warsaw, National Museum, inv. nos 234056-234057 MNW.

Description: Only fragments of the large cross composition are preserved but, according to Michałowski it is almost identical to no. 2. However, due to damage, it cannot be ascertained if Christ and the Living Creatures were part of the composition. A dark-skinned standing male figure (a donor?)¹⁰¹ is depicted in the lower left quarter of the cross. He is dressed in a light-coloured ankle long garment with long sleeves. Faint traces indicate a branch or staff in his right hand.

Inscriptions: illegible.

Literature: Michałowski 1967, 125; Jakobielski *et al.* 2017, cat. 52-52A (B. Mierzejewska/S. Jakobielski/M. Martens-Czarnecka).

13. Abdallah-n Irqi, Central Church, south-eastern part (in front of southern *pastophorium*), east wall (Pl. 15).

Date: tenth century.

Size: 1.81 m wide and 1.96 m high.

Present location: Aswan, Nubia Museum, inv. no. 11495.

Description: Light coloured Greek cross with slightly flared arms terminating in rounded transverse ends. The cross arms are studded with gemstones. On the intersection of the beams is a large oval with a bust of Christ, who holds a book in his left arm. The quarters are filled completely with the heads of the Four Living Creatures who are surrounded by wings which extend beyond the cross shape. Between the lowest pair of wings, a shaft points down. There is no trace of a base or spike preserved. A donor is depicted standing in the lower left-hand quarter. The dark-skinned man is dressed in a red ankle long garment with long wide sleeves and a pallium-like white overgarment. He holds a branch in his right hand, which is split up into three twigs with red fruit or flowers.

¹⁰¹ Afterwards, the dark skin was painted white (Jakobielski *et al.* 2017, 209).

Inscriptions: Greek. Names of the Creatures, three times *agios*. Prayer (request for help and protection).

Literature: van Moorsel 1966; van Moorsel *et al.* 1975, 33-34 (no. 1), 72 (6/4), 111-115, Pls 78-81; Kühnel 1992, 194, Fig. 3.

14. Faras, Cathedral, northern vestibule, west wall (Pl. 16).

Date: early eleventh century.

Size: ca. 150 cm above floor level, ca. 208 cm high (with base); vertical beam 158 cm high, horizontal beam 120 cm wide. Diameter of medallion: 34 cm. Present location: Warsaw, National Museum inv. no. 234018 MNW.

Description: The cross is almost identical to no. 4 (painted on the soffit of the arch to the northern vestibule, almost next to this cross). The part under the base was already damaged at the time of excavation. Due to the similarity to no. 4, the idea of the existence of a spike and head under hemisphere below the foot is convincing.

Inscriptions: Greek: *Stauros*, names of Christ and the Living Creatures, dedicatory inscription of a woman (Paimy, daughter of Anna).

Literature: Michałowski 1967, 161-162, Pl. 89; Jakobielski *et al.* 2017, cat. 76 (B. Mierzejewska/M. Martens-Czarnecka); <https://cyfrowe.mnw.art.pl/en/catalog/617964>; accessed 20 December 2022.

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